

THE SYNTACTIC POSITION OF THE INFINITIVE IN THE SENTENCE STRUCTURE

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Abstract. An infinitive is a verbal consisting of the word to plus a verb (in its simplest "stem" form) and functioning as a noun, adjective, or adverb. This article describes the syntactic position of the infinitive in the sentence structure.

Key words: Infinitive, formation of infinitive, syntactic position, sentence structure.

Infinitive is a linguistics term for certain verb forms existing in many languages, most often used as non-finite verbs. As with many linguistic concepts, there is not a single definition applicable to all languages. The word is derived from Late Latin *infinitivus*, a derivative of *infinitus* meaning "unlimited". In traditional descriptions of English, the infinitive is the basic dictionary form of a verb when used non-finitely, with or without the particle *to*. Thus *to go* is an infinitive, as is *go* in a sentence like "I must go there" (but not in "I go there", where it is a finite verb). The form without *to* is called the bare infinitive, and the form with *to* is called the full infinitive or *to*-infinitive.

Infinitives are a special form of verbs that can be used as a noun, adjective, or adverb. They are usually made by adding the word *to* before the base verb, and they can be useful when discussing actions without actually doing the action, such as "I want to go home," or "To err is human." The infinitive form is crucial to English and many other languages, but the grammar rules for infinitives can be tricky. In this guide, we explain all about the different types of infinitives and how to use them, including clear infinitive examples so you can see how they work. Infinitives are a form of verb that allow the word or a group of words to be used as a noun, adjective, or adverb. Every type of verb can be put into the infinitive form, even phrasal verbs.

Usually, infinitives are formed by adding the word *to* before the base form of the verb, as in *to be*, but sometimes the base form of the verb is used alone (we explain more in the next section). The purpose of infinitives is to discuss an action in general instead of a specific instance of the action being done. For example, take a look at these two sentences:

I need to win.

Today, we win.

The first sentence uses the infinitive form of the verb *win* as a noun; the main verb of the sentence is actually “need.” The second sentence uses the standard form of *win* as an actionable verb. In the first sentence with the infinitive, the action of “winning” is not actually done; the sentence simply discusses the idea of winning. The second sentence, however, describes the action of winning.

Following certain verbs or prepositions, infinitives commonly do have an implicit subject, e.g.:

- I want to eat them as dinner.
- For him to fail now would be a disappointment.

As these examples illustrate, the implicit subject of the infinitive occurs in the objective case (*them*, *him*) in contrast to the nominative case that occurs with a finite verb, e.g., “*They ate their dinner.*” Such accusative and infinitive constructions are present in Latin and Ancient Greek, as well as many modern languages. The atypical case regarding the implicit subject of an infinitive is an example of exceptional case-marking. As shown in the above examples, the object of the transitive verb “*want*” and the preposition “*for*” allude to their respective pronouns’ subjective role within the clauses.

While we already covered the main uses for both infinitive forms, there is some infinitive grammar that we haven’t covered yet. Below, we explain three key areas for understanding infinitive grammar: split infinitives, passive infinitives, and continuous infinitives. A split infinitive is a full infinitive that contains an adverb or adverbial phrase between *to* and the base verb, such as *to hungrily eat*.

Split infinitives are a debated topic among grammarians, with some saying they should be avoided and others saying there's nothing wrong with them. There's no official answer on whether or not they're correct. In most cases, we recommend avoiding them when you can and using them only in some scenarios. In general, you can communicate more clearly when you keep related words next to each other, so if you can move the adverb after the infinitive and it still makes sense, that's probably best.

*This app helps you to quickly, easily, and conveniently **work**.*

*This app helps you **to work** quickly, easily, and conveniently.*

Like other verbs, infinitives can also be written in the passive voice. In the passive construction, the subject of the verb becomes the receiver of the action instead of the doer. For passive infinitives, instead of the base verb use the word *be* + the past participle. For example, if you want to turn *to do* into a passive infinitive, use *to be done*. You can use passive infinitives with both full infinitives and bare infinitives.

*I was hoping **to be given** an A on my paper.*

Like verbs in the continuous tense, continuous infinitives represent an ongoing action. Instead of the base form of the verb, continuous infinitives use the word *be* + **the present participle** (the *-ing* form). For example, to make the infinitive *to do* into a continuous infinitive, use *to be doing*. Just like passive infinitives, continuous infinitives can be used for both full infinitives and bare infinitives.

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